

Species guide of *Scorpaena* species from the North-eastern Atlantic and Mediterranean.

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Abstract:

The family Scorpaenidae comprises a diverse group of venomous marine fishes with complex taxonomy and high morphological similarity, making accurate species identification challenging. Within this family, the genus *Scorpaena* represents one of the most species-rich and widely distributed groups, with particularly high diversity in the Atlantic basin. The North-eastern Atlantic and Mediterranean region hosts ten currently recognized *Scorpaena* species and is of special ecological, commercial, and public-health relevance due to intensive fisheries, human activity, and the venomous nature of these fishes. Existing identification resources for this region, notably those provided in *Fishes of the North-eastern Atlantic and Mediterranean* (Whitehead et al., 1986), are now outdated given taxonomic revisions, newly recorded species, and shifts in species distributions driven by environmental change. This work updates and supplements previous treatments by providing an illustrated, user-oriented identification key, revised diagnostic characters, and current distribution data. The guide is intended as a practical field and reference tool for researchers, fisheries managers, and educators, supporting accurate identification of *Scorpaena* species in the region.

Fig.1. Relative size representation (based on average species length) of three of the most commonly found *Scorpaena* species in the North-eastern Atlantic and Mediterranean. Top to bottom: *Scorpaena notata*, *Scorpaena porcus* and *Scorpaena scrofa*. Art by José Neto.

Introduction

The Scorpaenidae family is a moderately large cosmopolitan family of marine fishes found throughout tropical, subtropical and temperate waters. They are divided into 6 subfamilies Scorpaeninae, Caracanthinae, Pteroinae, Setarchinae, Sebastobinae and Sebastinae, with 388 recognized species within 39 different genera (Fricke et al., 2025; van der Laan & Fricke, 2025) (see **Appendices S.1.**).

While these classifications remain debated and disagreement persists regarding the taxonomic grouping within the family and subfamilies (Smith et al., 2018), members of the family share several diagnostic morphological traits, such as large heads (37-50% Standard Length), the presence of a suborbital ridge below the eye (an extension of the third infraorbital bone), numerous head spines, and striated swimbladder musculature, present even in species with vestigial or absent swimbladders (Poss, 1999). They also often exhibit shared distinctive ecological traits, being largely nocturnal benthic ambush predators, with solitary and mostly sedentary behaviour, and a coloration that exhibits cryptic patterns, superimposed on a generally red or reddish body, and often accompanied by dermal appendages that aid in camouflage (Santhanam, 2018). The most notable feature of this family, however, is the near-universal presence of a venomous apparatus associated with the spinous anterior part of the dorsal fin (VIII to XVIII spines), from which the common name “scorpionfishes”, and, by extension, the family name is derived. Some species also possess secondary venomous apparatus in the anal or pelvic fins (Santhanam, 2018). Indeed, Scorpaenidae is one of the most species-rich families of bony fish, with regard to the total number of venomous species, and may be the largest when considering only marine species.

While “scorpionfish” can refer to a vast number of species across several genera, some even outside of this family, for example see Dehaan et al. (1991), the term is most commonly associated with Scorpaenidae’s type genus, *Scorpaena*, sometimes referred to as “true scorpionfish”. Within the family, this is the second most species-rich genus, behind *Sebastes*, and currently comprises 62 identified species (see **Appendices S.2.**), that vary from small to relatively large body sizes, ranging from 10 to 50cm in total length.

Scorpaena presents the key features of the Scorpaenidae family, previously discussed, along with the following features. Most species possess a dorsal fin with XII venomous spines and 9 soft rays (XII-9), though the number of soft rays may vary from 7 to 11, with 8 or 10 being typical in some species or populations (Ferri et al., 2010; Fricke et al., 2020). Rarely, individuals may present XI or XIII dorsal spines (Wibowo & Motomura, 2022). The suborbital ridge has 3, rarely 4, suborbital spines. Anal fin with III spines and 5, rarely 4, soft rays. Pectoral fins with 13 to 21 rays, with the number of branched upper rays varying among species and increasing with individual age and size. Scales on the body are mostly ctenoid, sometimes cycloid, the head is largely naked, and the underside of the pectoral region is often scaleless, though depending on species. Tubular or pored scales follow along the lateral line. The head and body are often adorned with dermal appendages, most commonly tentacles and skin flaps, whose presence and size vary among species. These structures are usually associated with the supraorbital region, several of the cranial spines, the lower mandible, and the scales along the lateral line. *Scorpaena* lack a swimbladder and are therefore more benthic and sedentary than many other scorpionfishes, spending most of their time on or near the substrate and feeding opportunistically by ambushing potential prey (Santhanam, 2018).

Regarding their distribution, like Scorpaenidae in general, *Scorpaena* are found worldwide, in temperate, subtropical and tropical regions. However, although the family's highest species richness occurs in the tropical waters of the Indo-Pacific, the Atlantic appears to be the centre of diversity for the genus (Eschmeyer, 1969), with approximately 30 of the 62 recognized *Scorpaena* species occurring there. This pattern contrasts with the broader global trend outlined by Nelson et al. (2016), whereby fish diversity, though globally distributed, reaches its maximum in the Indo-West Pacific, particularly within the central Indo-Pacific region.

Fig.2. *Scorpaena* species distribution across the globe with red circles proportionate to the number of species in each region. Note the high diversity in the Atlantic basin compared to the larger Indo-Pacific region. The red circles represent overall centre of distribution for each species and not their entire distribution area (that information is provided in table **S.2. *Scorpaena* species list and distribution**). This distribution reflects the number of species per ocean basin and if they have a tropical or temperate affinity.

The genus appears to be most diverse in temperate to warm-subtropical waters. While some species occur in the tropics, they are typically either endemics with very limited ranges or species with extensive ranges that often also include temperate zones (range and distribution data from Fishbase (Froese & Pauly, 2025) and Eschmeyer Catalog of Fishes (Fricke et al., 2025) see references). Strictly temperate species, on the other hand, typically have moderate to broad ranges, though they rarely extend into the tropics. These distribution patterns may reflect broader differences in thermal niche preferences among *Scorpaena* and other Scorpaenidae genera. For instance, while *Scorpaena* dominates temperate to subtropical regions, *Sebastes* is primarily found in boreal and cold-temperate waters (Fernández-Zapico et al., 2012), and other prominent genera such as *Scorpaenopsis*, *Scorpaenodes* and *Pterois* occur mostly in tropical and subtropical waters, occasionally extending into warm-temperate zones (Fenner, 2004; Poss, 1999). These differential preferences may therefore explain why *Scorpaena* achieved particularly high diversity in Atlantic regions where other genera are less abundant. This likely reflects ecological partitioning, with these genera occupying distinct

thermal and habitat niches that reduce direct competition. Three main Atlantic hotspots for *Scorpaena* can be identified: (1) the tropical to subtropical West African coast, from Senegal to Namibia; (2) the western Atlantic, encompassing tropical to subtropical waters from the Carolinas and Florida through the Caribbean to São Paulo, Brazil and (3) the North-eastern Atlantic and Mediterranean.

The North-eastern Atlantic and Mediterranean region, as defined by Whitehead et al. (1986) “Fishes of the North-eastern Atlantic and Mediterranean” (FNAM), is of particular interest for the genus (see **Appendices S.3.**). This region is not only of high commercial importance, serving as a crossroads for three continents, but also contains key international shipping lanes, rich fishing grounds with important fishing stocks and the EEZs of several nations. The presence of *Scorpaena* species in this region represents both an opportunity and a potential conservation risk. Although venomous, all *Scorpaena* are edible (Poss, 1999) and therefore they constitute an exploitable food resource. At the same time, as the largest genus of venomous fish in the region (Özdemir et al., 2020; Turan et al., 2009), they pose a potential health hazard, since their pain-inducing venoms can temporarily incapacitate people, potentially limiting recreational and economic activities and generating associated human and financial costs (Haddad & Lopes-Ferreira, 2023; Harris et al., 2025; Valdoleiros et al., 2021). These risks are further exacerbated by the general lack of information and education regarding the presence and handling of venomous fishes (Harris et al., 2025; Raechel et al., 2024) as well as the lack of protocols of action and specific treatment for accidents with these species (Gweta et al., 2008; Portillo Stempel et al., 2009), which can sometimes give rise to unexpected secondary complications, such as idiosyncratic reactions to the venom, rare severe or long-lasting symptoms, and, in extreme cases, though for these species only demonstrated through experimental settings, death (Boletini-Santos et al., 2008; Campos et al., 2016; Carlson et al., 1973; Haddad et al., 2003; Schaeffer et al., 1971).

Given all the points discussed, it is essential to have accurate, up-to-date information on these species. This task is often challenging due to several factors: the difficulty of correctly identifying species within this family due to their high similarity, which can lead to misidentifications (Whitehead et al., 1986; Yedier & Bostanci, 2021a, 2021b), recent shifts in species distribution driven by human activities and climate change (Bédry et al., 2021; Needleman et al., 2018; Shakman, 2008), and, occasionally, the discovery of new species (Motomura et al., 2005; Wibowo & Motomura, 2022). Superimposed on these issues we also have the fact that these are cryptobenthic species which makes shifts in their distribution areas difficult to detect.

Taking all these factors into account, the present work aims to update and supplement the information on *Scorpaena* species provided by Whitehead et al. (1986) in FNAM, which remains a widely referenced and valuable resource for the identification of marine species, by providing an updated key with additional species present in the area, along with current distributions for the species. Here, an updated identification key is provided, incorporating additional species present in the area and current distribution data. This work is intended to serve as a comprehensive and practical tool for researchers, fishery managers, and educators, facilitating accurate identification, monitoring, and further study of the 10 *Scorpaena* species currently recognized in the area.

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3. Soft rays of dorsal fin (D- NR,**N**)
4. Supraorbital tentacle
5. Lateral line
6. Soft rays of caudal fin
7. Mandibular tentacles
8. Horizontal scale rows
9. Vertical scale rows
10. Pectoral fin
11. Hard spine of pelvic fin
12. Soft rays of pelvic fin
13. Hard spines of anal fin (A-**NR**,N)
14. Soft rays of anal fin (A-NR,**N**)
15. Body skin flaps

Fig.3. *Scorpaena* anatomy with focus on body parts used in species identification.

Fig.4. *Scorpaena* head anatomy with focus on spines used in species identification, image adapted from Wibowo & Motomura, 2022.

Fig.5. Inferior view of *Scorpaena* head and mandibular pores.

2. Identification key

- 1.a Occipital pit (**fig.4. 4**) absent.....2
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- 8.c Snout as large or larger than eye orbit; black spot in dorsal usually present; 18, rarely 17 or 19 rays; more than 20 rows of scales anterior to anus.....[Scorpaena stephanica \(X\)](#)

1. *Scorpaena azorica*

Vernacular name: Azores scorpionfish

	Atlantic	Mediterranean
Presence & distribution in the NAM region	Azores	Absent

IUCN: Data Deficient

Description

Characteristics: Head large; snout slightly shorter than orbit diameter; preorbital bone with 4 spines above the maxilla (**fig.4. 20-23**); 3 suborbital spines (**fig.4. 25**). Occipital pit well-developed (**fig.4. 4**). Fused mandibular pores (**fig.5. 3**). Supraorbital tentacle short (**fig.3. 4**), smaller than half the orbit diameter; no mandibular tentacles (**fig.3. 7**); body skin flaps poorly developed (**fig.3. 15**). DORSAL: 12 hard spines and 9 soft rays (D-XII,9). PECTORAL: 18 rays, 6 branched. Lateral line with 24 tubular spines. Ctenoid scales on body; 44 vertical scale rows (**fig.3. 9**), base of pectoral, chest and head without scales.

Species known only from the holotype.

Coloration: All fins spotted in dark, brown spots on head on lighter brown background, pale brown spots on the side of the body, dark pigmentation between soft dorsal fin and caudal fin. Dark spot on dorsal absent.

Maximum Length: 10cm

II. *Scorpaena canariensis*

Vernacular name: Canary scorpionfish

	Atlantic	Mediterranean
Presence & distribution in the NAM region	Madeira, Azores and Canary Islands	Absent

IUCN: Data Deficient

Description

Characteristics: Head large; snout of similar size to orbit diameter; preorbital bone with 2 spines above the maxilla (**fig.4. 20, 23**) PLS pointed forward (ventroanteriorly); 2 suborbital spines (**fig.4. 25**). Occipital pit absent (**fig.4. 4**). Separated mandibular pores (**fig.5. 2**). Supraorbital tentacle short (**fig.3. 4**); a few mandibular tentacles (**fig.3. 7**); body skin flaps poorly developed (**fig.3. 15**); small tentacles near preopercular spines (**fig.4. 27**). DORSAL: 12 hard spines and 9 soft rays (D-XII,9). PECTORAL: 16 rays, 5 or 6 branched. Lateral line with 25 or 26 tubular spines. Ctenoid scales on body; 66 to 69 vertical scale rows (**fig.3. 9**), base of pectoral and chest with scales.

Coloration: Clear background pinkish or off orange, with large darker blots of red or brown, sometimes also dotted with darker or clearer pigmentation. Pectoral and dorsal fins with similar pattern to body and without characteristic dark spot.

Maximum Length: 15cm

III. *Scorpaena elongata*

Vernacular name: Slender scorpionfish

	Atlantic	Mediterranean
Presence & distribution in the NAM region	Portugal expanding South along African coast, including Madeira and Canary Islands	Across, mostly in Western coast

IUCN: Least Concern

Description

Characteristics: Head large; snout slightly longer than orbit diameter; preorbital bone with 2 spines above the maxilla (**fig.4. 20, 23**); 3 or 4 suborbital spines (**fig.4. 25**). Occipital pit shallow (**fig.4. 4**). Separated mandibular pores (**fig.5. 2**). Supraorbital tentacle short (**fig.3. 4**); tentacles associated with preopercular spines (**fig.4. 16**); well-developed tentacles associated with preorbital bone (**fig.4. 20-23**); no mandibular tentacles (**fig.3. 7**); body skin flaps well-developed (**fig.3. 15**). DORSAL: 12 hard spines and 9 soft rays (D-XII,9). PECTORAL: 19 to 20 rays, rarely 18. Ctenoid scales on body; 45 to 50 vertical scale rows (**fig.3. 9**), base of pectoral, chest, and head without scales.

Coloration: Body with clear yellowish or pinkish base, darker reddish or brownish pigmentation distributed through the body. All fins spotted in dark, brown spots on head on lighter brown background, pale brown spots on the side of the body. Dorsal fin without characteristic dark spot.

Maximum Length: 50cm

IV. *Scorpaena laevis*

Vernacular name: Senegalese scorpionfish

	Atlantic	Mediterranean
Presence & distribution in the NAM region	Madeira, Azores and Canary Islands, Morocco South along African coast	Absent

A map showing the distribution of *Scorpaena laevis* in the Atlantic and Mediterranean regions. Red dots indicate the presence of the species along the West African coast, including the Madeira, Azores, and Canary Islands, and along the southern coast of Morocco. The Mediterranean Sea is shown to the east, where the species is absent.

IUCN: Least Concern

Description

Characteristics: Head large; snout of similar size with orbit diameter; preorbital bone generally with 3 spines above the maxilla (**fig.4. 20, 23**); 3 suborbital spines (**fig.4. 25**). Deep occipital pit (**fig.4. 4**). Separated mandibular pores (**fig.5. 2**). Supraorbital tentacle of variable size and branched, sometimes longer than orbit diameter (**fig.3. 4**); mandibular tentacles present (**fig.3. 7**); body skin flaps well-developed (**fig.3. 15**); tentacles near inferior preopercular spines (**fig.4. 27**). DORSAL: 12 hard spines and 9 soft rays (D-XII,9). PECTORAL: 18 to 20 rays. Cycloid scales on body; 40 to 45 vertical scale rows (**fig.3. 9**), lateral head, base of pectoral and chest scaled.

Coloration: Clear background pinkish or yellowish, with large darker blots of pink or brown pigments, head brownish. Back of dorsal fin without characteristic dark spot.

Maximum Length: 35cm

V. *Scorpaena loppei*

Vernacular name: Cadenat's scorpionfish

	Atlantic	Mediterranean
Presence & distribution in the NAM region	Northern Spain, south to Morocco, including Azores, Madeira and Canary Islands	Across

IUCN: Least Concern

Description

Characteristics: Head large; snout slightly shorter than orbit diameter; characteristic ridge on lateral surface of maxilla (**fig. 2. 24**); preorbital bone with 2 spines above the maxilla (**fig.4. 20-23**); 4 suborbital spines (**fig.4. 25**). Occipital pit well-developed (**fig.4. 4**). Fused mandibular pores (**fig.5. 3**). Supraorbital tentacle short (**fig.3. 4**), smaller than half the orbit diameter; no mandibular tentacles (**fig.3. 7**); body skin flaps poorly developed (**fig.3. 15**). DORSAL: 12 hard spines and 9 soft rays (D-XII,9). PECTORAL: 18 rays. Ctenoid scales on body; 35 to 40 vertical scale rows (**fig.3. 9**), base of pectoral, chest, and head without scales.

Coloration: All fins spotted in dark, brown spots on head on lighter brown background, pale brown spots on the side of the body. Dark spot between spines 6 and 9.

Maximum Length: 15cm

VI. *Scorpaena maderensis*

Vernacular name: Madeira scorpionfish

	Atlantic	Mediterranean
Presence & distribution in the NAM region	Portugal, south to Senegal, including Azores, Madeira and Canary Islands	Across

IUCN: Least Concern

Description

Characteristics: Head large; snout of similar size to orbit diameter; preorbital bone with 2 spines above the maxilla (**fig.4. 20, 23**) PLS pointed backwards (ventroposteriorly); 2 suborbital spines (**fig.4. 25**). Occipital pit absent (**fig.4. 4**). Separated mandibular pores (**fig.5. 2**). Supraorbital tentacle short (**fig.3. 4**); mandibular tentacles present (**fig.3. 7**); body skin flaps poorly developed (**fig.3. 15**); small tentacles near preopercular spines (**fig.4. 27**). DORSAL: 12 hard spines and 9 soft rays (D-XII,9). PECTORAL: 15 or 16 rays. Ctenoid scales on body; 52 to 56 vertical scale rows (**fig.3. 9**), base of pectoral and chest with cycloid scales.

Coloration: Clear background pinkish or off-orange, with large darker blots of red or brown, sometimes also dotted with darker or clearer pigmentation. Large clear bands along the body and in the base of the caudal peduncle. Pectoral and dorsal fins with similar pattern to body and without characteristic dark spot.

Maximum Length: 15cm

VII. *Scorpaena notata*

Vernacular name: Small red scorpionfish

	Atlantic	Mediterranean
Presence & distribution in the NAM region	Northern Spain, south to Mauritania, including Azores, Madeira and Canary Islands	Across

IUCN: Least Concern

Description

Characteristics: Head large; snout slightly shorter than orbit diameter; preorbital bone with 3 spines above the maxilla (**fig.4. 20-23**); 3 suborbital spines (**fig.4. 25**). Occipital pit present (**fig.4. 4**). Separated, but close together mandibular pores (**fig.5. 2**). Supraorbital tentacle short (**fig.3. 4**), smaller than half the orbit diameter; no mandibular tentacles (**fig.3. 7**); short tentacles near several parts of the head; body skin flaps poorly developed along parts of the lateral line (**fig.3. 15**). DORSAL: 12 hard spines and 9 soft rays (D-XII,9). PECTORAL: 17 to 18, rarely 19 rays. Ctenoid scales on body; 43 to 46 vertical scale rows (**fig.3. 9**), base of pectoral, chest, and head without scales.

Coloration: Pinkish or pale body with red or brown zones. All fins spotted in dark. Characteristic dark spot between spines 6 and 8 of first dorsal fin.

Maximum Length: 20cm

VIII. *Scorpaena porcus*

Vernacular name: Black scorpionfish

	Atlantic	Mediterranean
Presence & distribution in the NAM region	South British Isles and English Channel, South to Morocco, including Madeira, Azores and Canary Islands	Across

IUCN: Least Concern

Description

Characteristics: Head large; snout slightly shorter than orbit diameter; preorbital bone with 2 spines above the maxilla (**fig.4. 20-23**); 2 or 3 suborbital spines (**fig.4. 25**). Occipital pit well-developed (**fig.4. 4**). Separated mandibular pores (**fig.5. 2**). Supraorbital tentacle present (**fig.3. 4**), size similar with orbit diameter; no mandibular tentacles (**fig.3. 7**); short tentacles near several parts of the head; body skin flaps well-developed (**fig.3. 15**). DORSAL: 12 hard spines and 9 soft rays (D-XII,9). PECTORAL: 16 to 18 rays. Ctenoid scales on body; 65 to 70 vertical scale rows (**fig.3. 9**), base of pectoral, chest, and head without scales.

Coloration: Clear background yellowish or off orange, with large darker blots of red or brown, sometimes also dotted with darker pigmentation. Large paler bands on body and in the base of the caudal peduncle. Pectoral and dorsal fins with similar pattern to body sometimes small dark spot on dorsal.

Maximum Length: 40cm

IX. *Scorpaena scrofa*

Vernacular name: Red scorpionfish

	Atlantic	Mediterranean
Presence & distribution in the NAM region	British Isles and South Northern Sea, south to African Coast, including Madeira, Azores and Canary Islands	Across

IUCN: Least Concern

Description

Characteristics: Head large; snout slightly longer than orbit diameter; preorbital bone with 3 or 4 spines above the maxilla (**fig.4. 20, 23**); 2 to 4 suborbital spines (**fig.4. 25**). Occipital pit shallow (**fig.4. 4**). Separated mandibular pores (**fig.5. 2**). Supraorbital tentacle short or absent (**fig.3. 4**); tentacles associated with preopercular spines (**fig.4. 16**); well-developed tentacles associated with preorbital bone (**fig.4. 20-23**); mandibular tentacles present (**fig.3. 7**); body skin flaps generally present (**fig.3. 15**). DORSAL: 12 hard spines and 9 soft rays (D-XII,9). PECTORAL: 18 to 20 rays. Ctenoid scales on body; 45 vertical scale rows (**fig.3. 9**), base of pectoral, chest, and head without scales.

Coloration: Body with clear or pinkish base, reddish pigmentation distributed through the body. All fins spotted in dark, dark spot on dorsal fin.

Maximum Length: 60cm

X. *Scorpaena stephanica*

Vernacular name: Spotted-fin scorpionfish

	Atlantic	Mediterranean
Presence & distribution in the NAM region	Morocco South along African coast, including Madeira	Absent

IUCN: Least Concern

Description

Characteristics: Head large; snout slightly longer than orbit diameter; preorbital bone with 2 to 3 spines above the maxilla (**fig.4. 20-23**); 3 to 4 suborbital spines (**fig.4. 25**). Occipital pit well-developed (**fig.4. 4**). Separated, mandibular pores (**fig.5. 2**). Supraorbital tentacle short or absent (**fig.3. 4**), smaller than half the orbit diameter; no mandibular tentacles (**fig.3. 7**); short tentacles near several parts of the head; body skin flaps poorly developed along parts of the lateral line (**fig.3. 15**). DORSAL: 12 hard spines and 9 soft rays (D-XII,9). PECTORAL: commonly 18, rarely 17 or 19 rays, 6 to 9 rays branched. Ctenoid scales on body; 43 to 48 vertical scale rows (**fig.3. 9**), base of pectoral, chest, and head without scales.

Coloration: Pinkish or pale body with red or brown zones. All fins marked with dark spots. Characteristic dark spot between spines 6 and 10 of first dorsal fin.

Maximum Length: 45cm

3. Syntax table

Tab. 1. Syntax table of key identification characteristics. Key characteristics to distinguish similar species are signalled in green.

Species	Characteristics	Occipital pit	Nº of vertical scale rows	Pectoral zone	Lateral ridge of maxilla	Supraorbital tentacle	Mandibular tentacles	Dorsal blackspot	Orbit/Snout ratio	Mandibular pores	Posterior Lacrimal Spine	Max Size
<i>S. azorica</i>		Well-developed	44	Naked	Absent	Short	Absent	Present	Snout shorter	Fused	N/A	10cm
<i>S. canariensis</i>		Absent	66-69	Scaled	Absent	Short	Present	Absent	Similar	Separated	Forward	15cm
<i>S. elongata</i>		Underdeveloped	45-50	Naked	Absent	Short or absent	Absent	Absent	Snout longer	Separated	N/A	50cm
<i>S. laevis</i>		Well-developed	40-45	Scaled	Absent	Developed and branched	Present	Absent	Similar	Separated	N/A	35cm
<i>S. loppei</i>		Present	35-40	Naked	Present	Short	Absent	Present	Snout shorter	Fused	N/A	15cm
<i>S. maderensis</i>		Absent	52-56	Scaled	Absent	Short	Present	Absent	Similar	Separated	Backwards	15cm
<i>S. notata</i>		Present	43-46	Naked	Absent	Short	Absent	Present	Snout shorter	Separated	N/A	20cm
<i>S. porcus</i>		Well-developed	65-70	Naked	Absent	Developed	Absent	Present	Snout slightly shorter	Separated	N/A	40cm
<i>S. scrofa</i>		Underdeveloped	45	Naked	Absent	Short or absent	Present	Present	Snout longer	Separated	N/A	60cm
<i>S. stephanica</i>		Present	43-48	Naked	Absent	Short or absent	Absent	Present	Similar or snout longer	Separated	N/A	45cm

4. Appendices

S.1. Scorpaenidae

All subfamilies within the Scorpaenidae family, with their respective genera and number of species per genus. Taxonomic groups treated within this work underlined and in bold.

<i>Subfamily</i>	<i>Genus</i>	<i>Number of valid species</i>	
<u>Scorpaeninae</u>	Hipposcorpaena	1	
	Hoplosebastes	1	
	Idiastion	3	
	Iracundus	1	
	Neomerinthe	17	
	Neoscorpaena	1	
	Parascorpaena	8	
	Phenacoscorpius	9	
	Pogonoscorpius	1	
	Pontinus	20	
	Pteroidichthys	4	
	Rhinopias	6	
	<u>Scorpaena</u>	62	
	Scorpaenodes	29	
	Scorpaenopsis	29	
	Sebastapistes	12	
	Taenianotus	1	
	Thysanichthys	1	
	Ursinoscorpaenopsis	1	
	Caracanthinae	Caracanthus	5
Pteroinae	Brachypterois	3	
	Dendrochirus	2	
	Ebosia	4	
	Nemapterois	1	
	Neochirus	5	
	Parapterois	3	
	Pterois	5	
	Pteropterus	7	
	Setarchinae	Ectreposebastes	2
		Lioscorpius	4
Lythrichthys		5	
Setarches		1	
Sebastolobinae	Adelosebastes	1	
	Sebastolobus	3	
	Trachyscorpia	6	
Sebastinae	Helicolenus	9	
	Hozukius	2	
	Sebastes	109	
	Sebastiscus	4	

S.2. *Scorpaena* species list and distribution

List of all 62 recognized *Scorpaena* species as per Fricke et al. (2025) and their general distribution. Species presented in this guide and found in the North-Eastern Atlantic and Mediterranean in bold.

Species	Author citation	Ocean Basin	Specific Range
<i>Scorpaena afuerae</i>	Hildebrand, 1946	Eastern Pacific	Southern Mexico to Peru
<i>Scorpaena agassizii</i>	Goode & Bean, 1896	Western Atlantic	North Carolina to Brazil (including Gulf of Mexico and Caribbean)
<i>Scorpaena albifimbria</i>	Evermann & Marsh, 1900	Western Atlantic	Bermuda & Florida to Brazil (including Gulf of Mexico and Caribbean)
<i>Scorpaena angolensis</i>	Norman, 1935	Eastern Atlantic	Mauritania to Angola (including Cape Verde and São Tomé)
<i>Scorpaena annobonae</i>	Eschmeyer, 1969	Eastern Atlantic	Annobón Island (Endemic)
<i>Scorpaena ascensionis</i>	Eschmeyer, 1971	Central Atlantic	Ascension Island
<i>Scorpaena azorica</i>	Eschmeyer, 1969	Eastern Atlantic	Azores and Mediterranean Sea
<i>Scorpaena bergii</i>	Evermann & Marsh, 1900	Western Atlantic	New York to Northern Brazil (including Gulf of Mexico and Caribbean)
<i>Scorpaena brachyptera</i>	Eschmeyer, 1965	Western Atlantic	Florida to Brazil (including Caribbean)
<i>Scorpaena brasiliensis</i>	Cuvier, 1829	Western Atlantic	Virginia to Brazil (including Gulf of Mexico and Caribbean)
<i>Scorpaena brevispina</i>	Motomura & Senou, 2008	Northwestern Pacific	Pacific coast of Japan
<i>Scorpaena bulacephala</i>	Motomura, Last & Yearsley, 2005	Southwestern Pacific	Lord Howe Island to Vanuatu
<i>Scorpaena calcarata</i>	Goode & Bean, 1882	Western Atlantic	South Carolina to Brazil (including Gulf of Mexico and Caribbean)
<i>Scorpaena canariensis</i>	Sauvage, 1878	Eastern Atlantic	Azores, Madeira and Canary Islands
<i>Scorpaena cardinalis</i>	Solander & Richardson, 1842	Southwestern Pacific	New Zealand to Kermadec islands
<i>Scorpaena cocosensis</i>	Motomura, 2004	Eastern Pacific	Cocos Island and Galapagos Islands
<i>Scorpaena colorata</i>	Gilbert, 1905	Central Pacific	Johnston Atoll and Hawaiian Islands
<i>Scorpaena decemradiata</i>	Fricke, Golani, Appelbaum-Golani & Zajonz, 2018	Red Sea	Gulf of Aqaba (Endemic)
<i>Scorpaena dispar</i>	Longley & Hildebrand, 1940	Western Atlantic	South Carolina to Brazil (including Gulf of Mexico and Caribbean)
<i>Scorpaena elachys</i>	Eschmeyer, 1965	Western Atlantic	Florida to Panama
<i>Scorpaena elongata</i>	Cadenat, 1943	Eastern Atlantic, Mediterranean	Portugal to Namibia (including Macaronesia and São Tomé)
<i>Scorpaena fernandeziana</i>	Steindachner, 1875	Southeastern Pacific	Juan Fernández and Desventuradas Islands
<i>Scorpaena gasta</i>	Motomura, Last & Yearsley, 2006	Eastern Indian Ocean	Southwest Australia
<i>Scorpaena grandicornis</i>	Cuvier, 1829	Atlantic	Florida to Brazil & Central Atlantic Islands
<i>Scorpaena grattanica</i>	Trunov, 2006	Central Atlantic	Grattan Bank (near Ascension Island)

<i>Scorpaena guttata</i>	Girard, 1854	Eastern Pacific	Central California to Gulf of California
<i>Scorpaena histrio</i>	Jenyns, 1840	Eastern Pacific	Baja California to Chile (including Galapagos)
<i>Scorpaena inermis</i>	Cuvier, 1829	Western Atlantic	Florida and Bahamas to Brazil (including Caribbean)
<i>Scorpaena isthmensis</i>	Meek & Hildebrand, 1928	Western Atlantic	Quintana Roo (Mexico) to Brazil (including Caribbean)
<i>Scorpaena jacksoniensis</i>	Steindachner, 1866	Southwestern Pacific	Southern Queensland to Victoria (Australia)
<i>Scorpaena lacrimata</i>	Randall & Greenfield, 2004	South Pacific	Society Islands
<i>Scorpaena laevis</i>	Troschel, 1866	Eastern Atlantic	Mauritania to Congo (including Macaronesia and São Tomé)
<i>Scorpaena longaecrista</i>	Wibowo & Motomura, 2021	Eastern Indian Ocean	West Australia
<i>Scorpaena loppei</i>	Cadenat, 1943	Eastern Atlantic, Mediterranean	Bay of Biscay to Western Sahara (including Azores, Madeira)
<i>Scorpaena maderensis</i>	Valenciennes, 1833	Eastern Atlantic, Mediterranean	Portugal to Senegal (including Macaronesia)
<i>Scorpaena melasma</i>	Eschmeyer, 1965	Western Atlantic	Brazil
<i>Scorpaena mellissii</i>	Günther, 1868	Central Atlantic	Saint Helena (Endemic)
<i>Scorpaena miostoma</i>	Günther, 1877	Northwestern Pacific	Southern China to Southern Japan
<i>Scorpaena mystes</i>	Jordan & Starks, 1895	Eastern Pacific	Southern California to Chile (including Galapagos)
<i>Scorpaena nasicornua</i>	Fricke & Zhukov, 2020	Indian Ocean	Gulf of Aden
<i>Scorpaena neglecta</i>	Temminck & Schlegel, 1843	Indo-West Pacific	East Africa to Japan and Australia
<i>Scorpaena normani</i>	Cadenat, 1943	Eastern Atlantic	Mauritania to Angola (including São Tomé)
<i>Scorpaena notata</i>	Rafinesque, 1810	Eastern Atlantic, Mediterranean, Black Sea	Bay of Biscay to Senegal (including Macaronesia)
<i>Scorpaena onaria</i>	Jordan & Snyder, 1900	Indo-Pacific	Andaman Sea to Hawaii
<i>Scorpaena orgila</i>	Eschmeyer & Allen, 1971	Southeastern Pacific	Easter Island (Endemic)
<i>Scorpaena papillosa</i>	Schneider & Forster, 1801	Southwestern Pacific	Southeast Australia and New Zealand
<i>Scorpaena pepo</i>	Motomura, Poss & Shao, 2007	Northwestern Pacific	Taiwan to Mariana Islands and Southern Japan
<i>Scorpaena petricola</i>	Eschmeyer, 1965	Western Atlantic	[Range not specified in source]
<i>Scorpaena plumieri</i>	Bloch, 1789	Western Atlantic	New York to Brazil & Central Atlantic Islands
<i>Scorpaena porcus</i>	Linnaeus, 1758	Eastern Atlantic, Mediterranean, Black Sea	British Isles to Morocco (including Macaronesia)
<i>Scorpaena regina</i>	Wibowo, Johnson & Motomura, 2019	Southwestern Pacific	East coast of Queensland, Australia
<i>Scorpaena russula</i>	Jordan & Bollman, 1890	Eastern Pacific	Southern Baja California to Northern Peru
<i>Scorpaena scrofa</i>	Linnaeus, 1758	Widespread	Mediterranean, Eastern Atlantic, Indian Ocean
<i>Scorpaena sonora</i>	Jenkins & Evermann, 1889	Eastern Pacific	Southern Baja California to Oaxaca (Endemic)
<i>Scorpaena sororreginae</i>	Wibowo & Motomura, 2021	Eastern Indian Ocean	Northwest Australia

<i>Scorpaena stephanica</i>	Cadenat, 1943	Eastern Atlantic, Mediterranean	Mauritania to Angola (including Madeira and São Tomé)
<i>Scorpaena sumptuosa</i>	Castelnau, 1875	Eastern Indian Ocean	Southwest Australia
<i>Scorpaena thomsoni</i>	Günther, 1880	Southeastern Pacific	Juan Fernández and Desventuradas Islands
<i>Scorpaena tierrae</i>	Hildebrand, 1946	Eastern Pacific	Peru to Chile
<i>Scorpaena uncinata</i>	de Buen, 1961	Southeastern Pacific	Chile
<i>Scorpaena vesperalis</i>	Wibowo & Motomura, 2020	Eastern Indian Ocean	Southwest Australia
<i>Scorpaena wellingtoni</i>	Victor, 2013	Eastern Pacific	Galapagos Islands (Endemic)

S.3. North-eastern Atlantic and Mediterranean

Fig.6. The North-eastern Atlantic and Mediterranean region and its geographical limits as defined in Whitehead et al. (1986), *Fishes of the North-eastern Atlantic and the Mediterranean*. Including marginal seas and sub-basins (excluding the Sea of Azov). Canary Islands are also included. Map created with QGIS (QGIS.org, 2025).

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